

ISic1155

I.Sicily inscription 1155

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone (grey)

Object

tabula ansata

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 158

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Γάιε Σήιε
2. Πτολεμαΐε
3. Σαμαρεῦ
4. χαΐρε

Apparatus

Text of IGTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492768

EDCS 38000224

PHI 140640

PHI 178085

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

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Kokalos. 20: 218-264. At 6

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